

Data FAIR Working Session: Software—Moving Our Community to Accept Software/Code Sharing and Citation

Cultural challenges and Techniques to encourage sharing
and citation

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Topics

Software sharing culture

To encourage to share software
I must encourage myself

Reproducibility challenges

Machine learning researchers are prompt to share

- Growing so fast!
- A publication in repositories (arxiv) are faster than a journal publication
- Conference culture (IEEE, ACM.)
- Papers are publishing their code source
- Comparison of methods!

Tools that might help

- Papers with code
• <https://paperswithcode.com>
- OpenReview
• <https://openreview.net>
- CoRe2 environment
• <http://core2project.org/>

A screenshot of a 'Benchmarks' table with columns for 'name', 'category', 'best method', 'paper title', 'stars', 'code', and 'comment'. Below the table is a diagram titled 'Confirmable Reproducible Research (CoRe2) Environment' showing various tools like Datasverse, binder, encapsulator, and docker. To the right is a section titled 'OUR VISION' with text about standardizing research and making it easier to reproduce.

Why people are not sharing?

- Comp. Scientist focus on **algorithms**
 - So that anyone could implement their own version
- In Comp. Sci. papers are made to prove the method
 - All the setup to validate the method, performance, computational cost.
- Projects have become very complex to share/handle
- Other fields
 - Comp. Sci. is multidisciplinary and SW is used as material resource.
 - The results are the product and not the SW.

Do's and Don'ts

Software sharing culture

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Do's and Don'ts

Reproducibility challenges

- Unsuccessful to reproduce experiments (1500 researchers (Baker, 2016)).
 - > 70% third-party experiments
 - > 50% their own experiments
- Running 1.4 million Jupyter notebooks on GitHub (Pimentel et al., 2019)
 - 24.11% run without errors
 - 4.03% produced the same results.

Other challenges

- Some fields (e.g. biology) use too much scripts or executables
- How to handle with obsolescence SW?
 - e.g. Python v2 , Python v3
 - Java 7, 8 has added other programming paradigm
- What to do with source code obfuscation?
- Peer-review takes so long (~6 months in Physics field)
 - dataset, SW, new experiments, etc, etc is EXHAUSTING!
 - I have just forget how my own code works
- What to do when a source code seems “impossible” to run?

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Benchmarks Add a Result

TREND	DATASET	BEST METHOD	PAPER TITLE	PAPER	CODE	COMPARE
	PROTEINS	🏆 HGP-SL	Hierarchical Graph Pooling with Structure Learning			See all
	MUTAG	🏆 G_Inception	When Work Matters: Transforming Classical Network Structures to Graph CNN			See all
	NCI1	🏆 WKPI-kmeans	Learning metrics for persistence-based summaries and applications for graph classification			See all
	D&D	🏆 U2GNN (Unsupervised)	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks			See all
	ENZYMES	🏆 DSGCN-allfeat	Bridging the Gap Between Spectral and Spatial Domains in Graph Neural Networks			See all
	PTC	🏆 U2GNN (Unsupervised)	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks			See all
	IMDb-B	🏆 U2GNN (Unsupervised)	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks			See all
	COLLAB	🏆 U2GNN (Unsupervised)	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks			See all

OUR VISION

Given current constraints and the need for iterative review, data curation and successful verification of a replication package for a single manuscript requires **six hours** of labor on average.

With the CoRe2 environment, we hope to make the process more efficient and effective, so researchers can spend more time doing science.

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Benchmarks

NAME	STATUS	BEST METHOD	APPROX. TITLE	STATUS	CODE	COMMENT
PROTEASIS	✓	✓	Hybridized Graph Ranking with Graph Convolution	✓	✓	✓
METAG	✓	✓	Multi-Task Meta-Learning: Training General Networks	✓	✓	✓
NEO	✓	✓	Learning Meta-Models for performance based curriculum and adaptation to graph classification	✓	✓	✓
END	✓	✓	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks	✓	✓	✓
ENDHES	✓	✓	Shaping the Gap Between Spectral and Spatial Attention in Graph Neural Networks	✓	✓	✓
PTC	✓	✓	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks	✓	✓	✓
MSL-B	✓	✓	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks	✓	✓	✓
COLLAR	✓	✓	Universal Graph Transformer Self-Attention Networks	✓	✓	✓

Confirmable Reproducible Research (CoRe2) Environment

OUR VISION

Eliminate current constraints and the need for complex setup, data collection and successful verification of a replication package for a single manuscript request and release of data on average.

With the CoRe2 environment, we hope to make the process more efficient and effective, so researchers can spend more time doing science.

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Do's and Don'ts

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Avoid undirect citations (inconsistent ways)

- Could'nt find DOI?

Table 1: Details about the numerical PRNGs used for the experiments.

PRNG	Description
LCG [24]	Implemented using Equation $x_{n+1} = (ax_n + c) \bmod m$ and parameters $a = 25,214,903,917$, $c = 11$, and $m = 2^{48} - 1$, which are the default values within the Java library <code>java.util.Random</code> .
RANDU [24]	It is a variation of LCG. We used the parameters $a = 65,539$, $c = 0$, and $m = 2^{31}$.
Mersenne Twister [35]	We used a Java implementation given in https://cs.gmu.edu/~sean/research/mersenne/MersenneTwister.java Copyright (c) 2003 by Sean Luke.
SplitMix [46]	We used the implementation from the Java SDK http://hg.openjdk.java.net/jdk8/jdk8/jdk/file/tip/src/share/classes/java/util/SplittableRandom.java .
PCG [39]	We used a Java implementation given at https://github.com/KilianB/pcg-java .

SW versioning

keep energy for round revision

Good coding practices

Maybe you should have commented

Forgetting How Your Own Code Works

//TODO: Comment

O RLY? FunctionZero

Cutting corners to meet arbitrary management deadlines

Essential

Copying and Pasting from Stack Overflow

O'REILLY* *The Practical Developer*
@ThePracticalDev

Do. Or do not. There is no try.

Avoid Using Dark Patterns

O RLY? *You will*
@ThePracticalDev

Coming soon

Writing documentation

O RLY? *ToDo*
Someone else

```

else {
  if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Windows NT 6.1") !== -1) {
    this.isWin7 = true;
    this.detectedPlatform = "Windows 7"
  } else {
    if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Windows NT 6.2") !== -1) {
      this.isWin8 = true;
      this.detectedPlatform = "Windows 8"
    } else {
      if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Mac OS X 10.7") !== -1) {
        this.isOSX_SnowLeopard = true;
        this.detectedPlatform = "OSX 10.7"
      } else {
        if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Mac OS X 10.8") !== -1) {
          this.isOSX_MountainLion = true;
          this.detectedPlatform = "OSX 10.8"
        } else {
          if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Mac OS X 10.9") !== -1) {
            this.isOSX_MountainLion = true;
            this.detectedPlatform = "OSX 10.9"
          } else {
            if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Linux") !== -1) {
              this.isLinux = true;
              this.detectedPlatform = "Linux"
            } else {
              if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Windows Phone 8") !== -1) {
                this.isWinPhone8 = true;
                this.detectedPlatform = "Windows Phone 8"
              } else {
                if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Android") !== -1) {
                  this.isAndroid = true;
                  this.detectedPlatform = "Android"
                } else {
                  if (navigator.userAgent.indexOf("Android 2.3") !== -1) {
                    this.isAndroid_Gingerbread = true;
                    this.detectedPlatform = "Android 2.3"
                  }
                }
              }
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

```


Funny Source Code Comments

```

//
// Dear maintainer:
//
// When I wrote this code, only I and God
// knew what it was.
// Now, only God knows!
//
// So if you are done trying to 'optimize'
// this routine (and failed),
// please increment the following counter
// as a warning
// to the next guy:
//
// total_hours_wasted_here = 67
//

```


Shave Hours Off Any Project

Variable Naming

The hardest part of coding

O RLY? *Creative Var. Name*

Ctrl+c, Ctrl+v, simple right? Now there is 200 pages for that

Copying and Pasting from StackOverflow

Your code is sh!t

O RLY? *Make it sbittier*

Does it run? just leave it alone.

Writing Code that Nobody Else Can Read

O RLY? *The Definitive Guide*
@ThePracticalDev

Maybe they'll just go away on their own.

Ignoring Deprecation Warnings

O RLY? *A Practical Guide*
@ThePracticalDev

Not just cite SW

- But acknowledge SW that has been used during the research process,
 - so that others follows this behavior.

Avoid notebooks bad practices

- Most notebooks do not test their code
- Hinder reproducibility
 - out-of-order cells
 - non-executed code cells
 - the possibility of hidden states.
- Most repositories do not declare their dependencies

SW metadata for reproducibility

- Configurations and platform descriptions are also needed.

Focus on undergraduated students

- POLI-USP
 - TCC project

- Replications of papers
- Zoom meetings
- GitLab
- Stablish workflows

Existing members and groups

Members of ImageGatherer 8

- **Danton Ferreira Vellenich** @dantfv · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 4 months ago
- **Enrico Rausch Triñanes** @enrico.trinanes · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 6 months ago
- **Iago Fava** @iagofava · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 6 months ago
- **Jeaneth Machicao** @machicao It's you · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 7 months ago
- **Leticia Almeida** @leticiamancuzo · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 7 months ago
- **Luiz Diego Balduino** @luizdiego · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 6 months ago
- **Pedro Luiz Pizzigatti Corrêa** @pedro.correa2 · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 7 months ago
- **Willian Werner Angelo da Costa** @willian.costa1 · [satelitalTCC](#)
Given access 7 months ago

Share + Cite

=

Open science

Thanks

FUNDAÇÃO DE AMPARO À PESQUISA
DO ESTADO DE SÃO PAULO